

A PARAMETRIC FLOW VISUALISATION STUDY OF THE WET COMPRESSION MOULDING (WCM) PROCESS

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WET COMPRESSION MOULDING

Motivation

- Cost per part requires further reduction for continued adoption by industry of fibre-reinforced plastic composites
- The WCM process reduces the number of tool and processing steps
- Fundamental understanding is lacking for appropriate design of an WCM process

Figure 1: Schematic of WCM process

Process Benefits

- Short cycle times
(*Parallelisation: draping, infiltration and curing*)
- Suitability for industrial mass production
- Suitable for all fibre reinforcement types & arrangements
- High degree of automatability
- High degree of Programmability

WCM FLOW VISUALISATION FACILITY

- Bottom mould; Transparent, Top mould; Illuminating
- Dome attachment; mount pressure sensors

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of flow visualisation rig mounted in the Universal Testing Machine

FLOW FRONT PROGRESSION

Figure 3: Flow front progression of layout 0°UD captured using flow visualisation setup. Flow fronts are presented the following times after initiation of mould closing: (a) 73 s, (b) 88 s, (c) 96 s, (d) 98 s, (e) 101 s, (f) 108 s, (g) 111 s, (h) 120 s

PRESSURE EVOLUTION AS A FUNCTION OF STACK LAYOUT

Figure 4:(a) Pressure plot for LU1, and subplots for (b) 0°UD, (c) LU1 and (d) LU2 stack layouts

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Figure 5: Permeability flow front vs Pressure subplots for (a) 0°UD, (b) LU1 and (c) LU2 stack layouts

Benefits

- Visually monitor textile wetting, resin flow, track voids
- Measure local test fluid pressure
- Measure total compaction force on mould platens